

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MORPHOLOGY OF POLYOLEFIN COMPOSITES WITH COCONUT FLOUR

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SUMMARY

In this work the mechanical properties and the morphology of polyolefin/coconut flour composites with and without treatment were studied. In the HDPE/coconut flour composites, the addition of a copolymer improved the interfacial adhesion and increased the mechanical properties. For the PP/coconut flour composites, the variations were not significant.

Keywords: polyolefin, coconut flour, composite, high density polyethylene, morphology.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastics filled with fibers were first introduced in the plastics market with the intention of producing new materials for engineering applications, and for substituting composites based on thermosetting resins. In the last two decades, the studies on thermoplastics reinforced with natural fibers have been intensified due to the increase on environment protection issues and on the strong international regulations. Natural fibers have received great attention as possible substitutes of synthetic fibers such as glass fiber [1-7]. Among the advantages of the natural fibers one can site: low cost, low density, good thermal isolating properties, being recyclable and a renewable source that does not affect the environment.

In general, the synthetic plastics are modified with natural fillers in order to make them environmentally friendly, since the increasing amount of waste and the low availability of landfills turn out the use of natural resources a responsible issue. However, when a hydrophilic nature fiber is included into a non polar polymer matrix (hydrophobic) several problems are encountered due to incompatibility which affect the fiber-polymer adhesion, thus resulting composites with poorer mechanical properties. With the intention of improving the interaction between the fiber and the polymer, several treatments have been proposed, among which we can mention the use of coupling agents [8-9]; the acetylating of fibers [10-11]; treatments with plasma, etc. Also, the addition of copolymers and functionalized polymers can improve the fiber-polymer interaction. These modifications permit to improve the mechanical behavior of the composites so they can have a better final application performance.

From all the fibers studied up to now, just a few studies are based on coconut flour, being this fiber present in great amounts in Venezuela. For this reason, this work had

the intention of studying the addition of coconut flour with and without treatment to polypropylene (PP) and high density polyethylene (HDPE) through the evaluation of the mechanical properties and morphology of their composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Polypropylene J600 (PP) (Melt flow index 7.0 dg/min, 230/2.16) and high density polyethylene Venelene 2908 (HDPE) (Melt flow index 7.3 dg/min, 190/2.16) were supplied by Polinter-Venezuela. Coconut flour of two different particle sizes (25-35 and >50 mesh) was supplied by Coconut Products, C.A.-Venezuela. As compatibilizing agents two copolymers of olefin-acrylic acid: one based on ethylene for the HDPE/coconut flour composite (with 18% w/w of acrylic acid), and the other based on propylene for the PP/coconut flour composite (Polybond 1001, with 6% w/w of acrylic acid) were used. A coupling agent titanate type, commercially known as Lica 12, supplied by Kenrich Petrochemicals, Inc., Bayonne, N.J., U.S.A. was used.

Procedure

Composites of polypropylene (PP) and of high density polyethylene (HDPE) with coconut flour of two different particle sizes (25-35 and >50 mesh) and in different proportions (5, 10, 15 and 20% w/w) were prepared. The composites were prepared in a Berstorff corotating twin screw extruder, model ECS, with a temperature of 210 °C at the fusion zone and a screw rotor speed of 110 rpm. Previous to mixing, the coconut flour was dried in a vacuum oven at 80 °C during 20 hours. Then, injection moulded specimens were fabricated for tensile testing in a Reed-Prentice 100TE injection moulding machine at 160 °C.

It was determined that 15% filler content and >50 mesh particle size gave the best results with respect to tensile properties and extrusion processing characteristics. Then, we focussed on how to improve the polymer-fiber adhesion through the use of different treatments to the filler. These treatments were the following: a) washing with NaOH. This treatment was done taking as reference the procedure followed by Ramaraj [12], at two different concentrations of NaOH (5 and 18 wt%); b) acetylating of the coconut flour. This treatment was based on the procedure used by Bello et al [11]; c) addition of a coupling agent. A titanate solution (Lica 12) at 10% was prepared. The amount of titanate must correspond to 1% of the flour mass; and d) the incorporation of an olefin-acrylic acid copolymer. The amount incorporated corresponds to 5% of the coconut flour mass.

The composites prepared were evaluated by tensile testing following the ASTM D638 standard procedure in a Lloyd Instruments equipment. Also, the morphology of the composites was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy using a Hitachi microscope, model S-500.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the microphotographs of the coconut flour particles for the two size ranges employed in this work. As we can see, the coconut flour with particle size between 25-35 mesh is more porous than the particles bigger than 50 mesh. This fact influenced negatively the mixing stage in the extruder; controlling the incorporation of the coconut flour was difficult due to its lower density, so the real percentage of filler in the composites was less than the theoretical value calculated to be added. As a consequence, the mechanical properties did also result in values lower than expected. In spite of this fact, we only report the results obtained for the composites prepared with coconut flour with a particle size >50 mesh.

Figure 1. Microphotographs of the coconut flour particles: (a) 25-35 mesh and (b) > 50 mesh.

In Tables 1 and 2 we report the mechanical properties of the PP/coconut flour and HDPE/coconut flour composites for different proportions of filler. We can appreciate that; in general, there is an increase in the Young's modulus when the filler content increases, as expected when a material of greater stiffness is added to a polymer. Nonetheless, in most of the cases, the values are lower than the value of the corresponding polymer matrix, possibly due to the interference of the filler on the stress propagation through the matrix and to the formation of filler agglomerates, fact that can be corroborated when we analyze the low elongation at break values of all the composites.

With respect to the elongation at break, similar results have been published by Yam et al [13], Selke [14] and Raj et al [15], whom studied the properties of polyethylene/woodflour composites. The possible reasons these researchers argument for this behaviour are that when a corrotating twin screw extruder is used, the processing conditions can destroy the fibers, and also, the leak of adhesion between fibers and polymer matrix. In addition, the hydrophilic nature of the natural fibers combined with the hydrophobic character of most of thermoplastics avoids the dispersion of the fiber on the matrix and the adhesion between these two components.

Nonetheless, considering that what we are incorporating to the polymer matrix is a waste material, one could say that the tensile properties, except the elongation at break, result equivalent to that of the pure polymer when 15% of coconut flour is added. In that sense, in search of better polymer-fiber interactions, new composites were prepared with 15% of coconut flour treated according to the following methods: washing with NaOH at concentrations of NaOH at 5 and 18 wt%); acetylating of the coconut flour; addition of a titanate type coupling agent (Lica 12) and the incorporation of an olefin-acrylic acid copolymer (EAA).

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the PP/coconut flour composites with different filler proportion.

Filler proportion	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
0	1559		
5	1387	25.6	10.0
10	1551	25.1	6.4
15	1587	24.7	8.0
20	1541	22.4	4.6

The standard deviation was never superior to 10% in all cases.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the HDPE/coconut flour composites with different filler proportion.

Filler proportion	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
0	552	12.1	153.6
5	485	11.3	119.1
10	496	12.3	37.4
15	577	19.4	12.3
20	612	18.7	11.6

The standard deviation was never superior to 10% in all cases.

Tables 3 and 4 present the values of the mechanical properties of the composites with respect to the filler treatment. Concerning the PP/coconut flour composites, it can be observed that there were no significant variations when all the different treatments were applied. However, in the HDPE/coconut flour composites, the Young's modulus and the tensile strength increased with respect to the untreated composite, except when titanate was used. The tendency obtained indicates that the composite with the ethylene-acrylic acid copolymer gives the greater modulus, followed by the blend with the acetylated coconut flour, and the flour treated with NaOH at 5%; representing an increase in this property of approximately 42%. This behaviour is contrary to the one exposed by Brahmakumar et al [4], who found that the composite with the untreated fiber exhibited a greater modulus than the composite with the fiber free of wax (immerse in an aqueous solution of NaOH at 5% during 84 hours); these results suggest that when the impurities present in the coconut flour are eliminated, a better matrix-filler interaction is achieved,

improving the compatibility between both components. On the other hand, Ichazo et al [10] found that for polyolefin composites with sisal fiber, the acetylation of the fiber improved the modulus of the mentioned composites due to the increased adhesion between the fiber and the polymeric matrix, agreeing with the results obtained in this investigation.

Table 3. Mechanical properties of the PP/coconut flour composites, with and without treatment (15 % filler, > 50 mesh).

Filler treatment	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
---	1587	24.7	5.8
NaOH 5%	1510	24.7	4.8
NaOH 18%	1562	26.9	6.5
Copolymer	1613	25.3	6.7
Titanate	1444	24.6	8.4
Acetylation	1382	26.4	6.7

The standard deviation was never superior to 10% in all cases.

Table 4. Mechanical properties of the HDPE/coconut flour composites, with and without treatment (15 % filler, > 50 mesh).

Filler treatment	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
---	882	19.4	12.3
NaOH 5%	1219	32.2	5.2
NaOH 18%	1045	30.7	6.6
Copolymer EAA	1282	33.3	5.3
Titanate	790	26.4	6.5
Acetylation	1251	31.3	6.6

The standard deviation was never superior to 10% in all cases.

On the other hand, in the HDPE/coconut flour composites, a notorious increase in the tensile strength is also appreciated as a consequence of the better polymer-filler interactions. Nonetheless, in Figure 2 we can see that for both treatments with NaOH (5 and 18%) the HDPE-coconut flour interaction remains weak. It is possible that the elimination of wax and impurities present on the coconut flour could be a decisive factor on the improvement on the tensile strength. Finally, an improvement in the polymer-filler interaction is clearly evidenced when the treatment with the EAA copolymer was employed.

Figure 2. Morphology of the fracture surface of HDPE composites with 15 wt% of coconut flour: a) untreated, b) with EAA copolymer, c) with NaOH 5% and d) with NaOH 18%.

CONCLUSIONS

It is possible to obtain polyolefin (PP and HDPE) composites with coconut flour that, in general, maintain similar mechanical properties to those of the pristine polymers. This fact would permit to fabricate cheaper products since a waste material is included; besides, the coconut flour comes from natural sources, so a biodegradable character would be added to the final application obtaining important environmental advantages. Also, the Young's modulus and tensile strength of the HDPE/coconut flour composites would significantly increase adding an ethylene-acrylic acid copolymer by improving notoriously the polymer-filler interaction.

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